

Effect of ultrasonic activation duration on micro-CT density of Well-Root™ PT apical plugs

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Abstract

The density and adaptation of the apical plug material during endodontic treatment of immature teeth are critical for minimizing microleakage and ensuring dimensional stability. This study assessed how different condensation techniques affect the micro-CT-measured density of apical plugs created with Well-Root™ PT. Apical plugs (5 mm thick) were created in 48 identical 3D-printed maxillary incisor models, split into four groups: manual condensation and indirect ultrasonic activation for 3, 9, or 15 s. Micro-CT analysis showed median densities of 11.3 g/cm³ for manual condensation, 10.4 g/cm³ for both 3- and 9-s ultrasonic activation, and 10.8 g/cm³ for 15-s ultrasonic activation. The 15 s ultrasonic group showed density comparable to manual ($p > 0.05$) and significantly higher than shorter ultrasonic durations ($p < 0.05$). In conclusion, prolonged indirect ultrasonic activation (15 s) enhanced the micro-CT density, likely through improved particle packing, expulsion of entrapped air or water, and calcium silicate hydrate reorganization. Short-duration ultrasonic activation resulted in lower density.

Keywords

Apical plug, calcium silicate cement, density, micro-CT, ultrasonic activation

Introduction

Endodontic management of immature permanent teeth is challenging due to their incomplete root development, wide open apices, and thin dentinal walls, which increase the risk of root fracture and complicate canal debridement and obturation (Mohammadi 2011; Duan et al. 2024). Traditional obturation methods are limited in these cases because the absence of an apical stop makes it difficult to achieve a reliable apical seal, and the thin dentinal walls are prone to fracture, especially with long-term calcium hydroxide use (Mohammadi 2011; Duan et al. 2024).

Apical plug creation with materials such as mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), Biodentine, or bioceramic putty is essential for forming an artificial barrier at the

root apex, enabling complete canal obturation, promoting periapical tissue healing, and supporting long-term treatment success (Ree and Schwartz 2017; Sharma et al. 2018; Ghaly et al. 2025). Clinical studies demonstrate that apical plug techniques result in high rates of periapical healing and long-term retention of the tooth, with MTA and newer bioceramic materials showing satisfactory outcomes in terms of apical sealing and radiographic healing (Ree and Schwartz 2017; Ghaly et al. 2025).

The density and adaptation of the apical plug material are critical for minimizing microleakage and ensuring dimensional stability, as external voids at the plug–canal interface compromise the apical seal and may permit microbial leakage (Ghaly et al. 2025). The density of calcium silicate-based materials or cements used for apical

plug formation is directly influenced by their chemistry, particularly the phase composition, particle size, and the presence of additives or radiopacifiers. Materials with a higher proportion of tricalcium silicate (C_3S) and dicalcium silicate (C_2S) tend to form a denser microstructure upon hydration, as these phases hydrate to produce calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel and calcium hydroxide, which fill the interstitial spaces and reduce porosity (Chen et al. 2009; Marciano et al. 2016; Shah et al. 2022).

The incorporation of ultrafine tricalcium silicate powder increases packing density and reduces pore volume, resulting in a material with higher compressive strength and lower porosity, which is a proxy for increased density (Shah et al. 2022). Conversely, the addition of radiopacifiers (zirconium oxide and tantalum pentoxide) and other fillers can alter the density depending on their concentration and particle size, sometimes increasing radiopacity but potentially introducing microvoids if not well integrated (Marciano et al. 2016; Zamparini et al. 2019).

The water-to-powder ratio during mixing also affects density: higher water content increases porosity and decreases density, whereas lower water content yields a denser set material but may compromise handling and injectability (Cahyanto et al. 2023). The formation of hydration products and the degree of cement hydration further modulate density, with more complete hydration leading to a denser matrix (Chen et al. 2009).

There is a direct correlation between the technique used for apical plug placement and the density of tricalcium silicate-based cements. Techniques that improve condensation and reduce porosity—such as ultrasonic activation—result in higher-density plugs, whereas bulk and incremental placement methods tend to produce lower density due to increased porosity and microvoids (Celikten et al. 2022). Ultrasonic activation achieves better particle packing and adaptation to dentin, minimizing voids and increasing the material's density, especially for MTA and BioAggregate. In contrast, Biodentine's density is less affected by placement technique, likely due to its intrinsic physicochemical properties (Celikten et al. 2022).

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) density measurements for calcium silicate cements are accurate for quantifying mineral density and volumetric changes, especially when calibrated against hydroxyapatite phantoms or aluminum standards (Orhan et al. 2021; Salcedo et al. 2021). For example, micro-CT-derived porosity and volumetric loss have been shown to predict mechanical strength and long-term stability of calcium silicate cements in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models (Ashi et al. 2023; Janini et al. 2025). In clinical contexts, increased mineral density measured by micro-CT after application of calcium silicate cements is associated with improved dentine remineralization and bioactivity (Pires et al. 2018). Despite these advances, the optimal placement technique to maximize density remains underexplored, particularly with varying ultrasonic activation durations, which could enhance material performance and reduce clinical risks in immature teeth.

Aim

The aim of this *in vitro* study was to compare the micro-CT density of calcium silicate cements for apical plugs, condensed manually and with ultrasonic activation of 3, 9, and 15 s. The null hypothesis was that the different condensation techniques create similar a density of the apical plugs.

Material and methods

Sample size calculation

Based on previous studies (Odabasi Tezer et al. 2024; Eldehna et al. 2025), and using G-Power statistical power analysis software (version 3.1.9.7), a total sample size of $n = 48$, divided into 12 per group, was calculated to be adequate to detect a large effect size ($W = 0.48$) with a statistical power ($1-\beta$ error) of 0.95 (95%) and a significance level (α error) of 0.05 (5%) for a hypothesis test.

Sample preparation

In this study, uniform 3D-printed replicas of immature maxillary first incisors with prepared endodontic access openings and measuring 21 mm long (DRSK, Hässleholm, Sweden) served as the experimental models. The apical portion of the root had a blunderbuss shape with an apical canal width of 2 mm. The replicas were mounted in a dedicated endodontic training system (Protrain, Simit Dental Srl, Mantova, Italy) using silicone-based impression material (Fig. 1). Apical plugs were created by a single operator under magnification with a dental operative microscope (Zumax OMS1800, Zumax Medical, Jiangu, China). This study used the premixed bioceramic putty Well-Root™ PT (Vericom, Chuncheon, Republic of Korea). The calcium-silicate cement was condensed via a suitably dimensioned endodontic plugger (Dentsply Sirona, Bensheim, Germany) to form a 5-mm-thick layer in the apical zone. For the groups involving ultrasonic condensation, a uniform tip (size 20, non-abrasive, made of stainless steel) was applied at a consistent 25 kHz intensity level. The study groups are presented in Table 1. The samples were then kept in an incubation chamber at 37 °C with full (100%) humidity for seven days to facilitate thorough setting of the material and mimic the intraoral physiological environment. In cases of extrusion of material through the apex, the surplus was removed using a surgical blade.

The three ultrasonic activation durations (3, 9, and 15 s) were deliberately chosen to span short, moderate, and extended times relative to the commonly reported 10–20 s range for calcium silicate-based materials (Sisli and Ozbas 2017; Aguiar et al. 2019). The 3 s interval was selected to assess whether brief activation could enhance material flow and compaction while minimizing risks such as heat generation or structural disruption, in line

Figure 1. Isolating the region of interest and measuring the density of the samples.

Table 1. Distribution of the study groups based on the condensation technique.

Group	Group 1 – Manual	Group 2 – 3 s US	Group 3 – 9 s US	Group 4 – 15 s US
Parameter				
Sample size	12	12	12	12
Apical plug material	Well-Root™ PT (premixed bioceramic putty, 0.25 g compule)			
Key ingredients	Calcium silicate compound; zirconium oxide; calcium sulfate dehydrate; calcium sodium phosphosilicate; polyethylene glycol; polypropylene glycol			
Condensation technique	Manual condensation using endodontic plugger	Indirect ultrasonic vibration via ultrasonic tip in contact with the plugger	Indirect ultrasonic vibration via ultrasonic tip in contact with the plugger	Indirect ultrasonic vibration via ultrasonic tip in contact with the plugger
Ultrasonic parameters	None	25 kHz, 3 s	25 kHz, 9 s	25 kHz, 15 s

with previous reports on 2–8 s ultrasonication (Sisli and Ozbas 2017). The 9 s duration served as an intermediate step to evaluate potential gains or drawbacks of moderate prolongation. Finally, the 15 s interval represented the upper end of standard protocols and acted as a reference for longer activation.

Scanning protocol

To quantify the density of the apical barrier, the specimens were scanned with a desktop micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) scanner (SkyScan 1272, Bruker, Kontich, Belgium). The plastic immature tooth models were firmly fixed in a custom sample holder to maintain uniform orientation throughout the scanning procedure. The apical plugs were scanned at 85 kV tube voltage, 117 μ A beam current, an aluminum attenuation filter with 1 mm thickness, and 9- μ m voxel resolution. The scan orbit was 360 degrees with a rotation step of 0.9° and an average of 4 frames per view. Each sample was scanned for approximately 10 minutes. Reconstruction of the projection data into transverse sections was accomplished using NRecon software (version 2.2.0.6, Bruker, Kontich, Belgium). Beam hardening and post-scan corrections for slow geometric change were applied. To measure the density of the apical plugs, a rod pair of 0.3 and 1.25 g/cm³ calcium hydroxyapatite (HA) were scanned, and the images were reconstructed with the same parameters. The images were used to convert the gray-level values into density values (Fig. 1). For this purpose, the images were binarized and loaded as the region of interest. The density was integrated over all cross-sectional levels within the volume of interest. The region of interest (ROI) was strictly limited to the apical plug material only, excluding the surrounding 3D-printed model.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted with SPSS v19.0 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA). The Shapiro–Wilk test was used to assess the data normality. A Kruskal–Wallis test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in the calculated density across the compared groups. Dunn’s test with Bonferroni adjustments was applied for multiple comparisons within the different groups. A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

Results

The density of apical plugs created with manual or ultrasonic condensation with different activation times is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Density of apical plugs (g/cm³) created with manual or ultrasonic condensation with different activation times (IQR: interquartile range, 25th–75th percentile).

Group	Description	Median (g/cm ³)	IQR (g/cm ³)
Group 1	Manual condensation	11.3	10.4–11.5
Group 2	3 s US	10.4	10.3–10.5
Group 3	9 s US	10.4	10.3–10.6
Group 4	15 s US	10.8	10.6–11.0

Table 3 presents pairwise comparisons of apical plug density with different condensation techniques.

Table 3. Pairwise comparisons of apical plug density with different condensation techniques (Kruskal–Wallis test, Dunn post hoc test with Bonferroni adjustments).

Comparison	<i>p</i> -value
Manual vs. 3 s US	0.018
Manual vs. 9 s US	0.025
Manual vs. 15 s US	0.980
3 s US vs. 9 s US	0.971
3 s US vs. 15 s US	0.008
9 s US vs. 15 s US	0.012

Density values varied significantly between manual condensation (Group 1) and short-duration ultrasonic activation (Groups 2 and 3), with the manual technique exhibiting the highest median density. Both 3 s and 9 s ultrasonic activation achieved a density of approximately 10.4, reflecting enhanced particle packing and void reduction. Group 4 (15 s ultrasonic) showed the highest density among ultrasonic groups, but it was not significantly different from manual condensation (*p* = 0.98).

Discussion

The current study measured the micro-CT density of apical plugs created with manual or ultrasonic condensation at different durations. Prolonged ultrasonic activation (15 s) produced the highest median density (10.8 g/cm³), statistically

comparable to manual condensation (11.3 g/cm^3 , $p = 0.98$) and significantly higher than the shorter activation groups (both 10.4 g/cm^3 , $p < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was partially rejected. These findings suggest that extended indirect ultrasonic vibration improves particle packing and microstructural homogeneity of Well-Root™ PT, although the absolute density values are relative to HA calibration and may be influenced by the specific radiopacifier (zirconium oxide) present in the material.

Tricalcium silicate-based cements, including mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), Biodentine, Well-Root PT, and NeoMTA Putty, are widely used in endodontics for apical plug formation due to their favorable physicochemical and biological properties. The baseline density of an apical plug is primarily determined by the material's composition, particle size distribution, and homogeneity. Optimized particle size and uniformity, as seen in Biodentine and ultrafine tricalcium silicate formulations, enable tighter packing and more complete hydration, resulting in higher density and improved mechanical strength (Camilleri et al. 2013; Duan et al. 2024).

Hydration is a critical process in these cements. In this study, samples were kept in an incubator with 100% humidity to ensure they remained properly hydrated during the setting process. Water reacts with tricalcium silicate to form calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) and calcium hydroxide. The formation of C-S-H fills interstitial spaces between unhydrated particles, increasing density and volumetric stability. The rate and completeness of hydration are influenced by particle size, with smaller particles hydrating more rapidly and thoroughly (Camilleri et al. 2013; Duan et al. 2024; Wu et al. 2024). The presence of calcium carbonate and accelerators (such as CaCl_2) in Biodentine further enhances hydration kinetics and density (Camilleri et al. 2013).

Canal moisture is a key factor in the setting and densification of hydraulic cements. Adequate moisture promotes hydration and densification, whereas over-drying can inhibit hydration, and excessive moisture may dilute the material, both leading to reduced density and increased porosity (Prati and Gandolfi 2015; Koutroulis et al. 2019). Tricalcium silicate cements are designed to set in moist environments, but the balance of moisture is critical for optimal physical properties (Formosa et al. 2012; Prati and Gandolfi 2015).

Consistency during apical plug creation affects density and stability. Materials with a putty-like consistency (NeoMTA Putty) maintain higher density and resist volumetric changes, whereas creamier or more fluid materials (Well-Root PT) may lose density if not properly manipulated (Camilleri et al. 2013; Wu et al. 2024). Dimensional stability is essential for maintaining a dense plug. Materials that resist deformation after placement preserve their shape and density over time (Formosa et al. 2012). Particle size and homogeneity are directly linked to density. Ultrafine, uniform particles allow for tighter packing and more complete hydration, whereas coarse or irregular particles can leave microvoids, reducing density and mechanical properties (Camilleri et al. 2013; Duan et al. 2024). The addition and distribution of radiopacifiers are necessary for clinical radiopacity but can affect setting time, density,

and microstructure. Poorly distributed radiopacifiers may create microgaps and compromise density (Khalil et al. 2016; Xuereb et al. 2016; Queiroz et al. 2021).

In the current study, Well-Root PT apical plugs demonstrated micro-CT density values ranging from 10.4 to 11.3 g/cm^3 when calibrated against a hydroxyapatite phantom, with manual condensation and 15 s ultrasonic activation achieving the highest values. These findings indicate that, contrary to initial expectations, prolonged ultrasonic vibration enhances material consolidation beyond short-duration activation (3 s and 9 s). The significant density improvement in the 15 s group over shorter ultrasonic durations may be attributable to sustained mechanical energy facilitating the expulsion of entrapped air and excess water, possibly promoting deeper C-S-H gel penetration into microstructural voids. The prolonged mechanical energy input could enhance the migration and reorganization of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel, allowing better interstitial filling and a more compact microstructure. Additionally, the gradual release of excess mixing water during extended activation might reduce internal porosity without compromising the hydraulic setting reaction, ultimately yielding a denser, more homogeneous set material compared to shorter activation durations or manual condensation alone.

Comparative micro-CT analyses of similar calcium silicate cements report porosity values of 1.93% for Well-Root PT, higher than Biodentine (1.22%) and MTA Biorep (0.57%) (Ashi et al. 2023), which inversely correlates with density. Other formulations, including iRoot BP Plus, Biodentine, and ProRoot MTA, exhibit total porosity between 5.91% and 9.58% (De Souza et al. 2013)—substantially greater than the near-zero porosity of hydroxyapatite phantoms used as calibration standards (Yong et al. 2022). The density values observed in this study are consistent with the hydraulic nature of these cements, which inherently contain microstructural voids despite optimization. However, the ultrasonic-induced density gains, particularly at 15 s, suggest a possible reduction in void volume, potentially enhancing apical seal integrity and resistance to microleakage.

As with any *in vitro* investigation, certain limitations should be acknowledged. The use of simulated 3D-printed immature root models, while providing standardization and reproducibility, does not fully replicate the complex physiological environment of the human oral cavity, including blood flow, tissue fluid dynamics, and masticatory forces. Consequently, the condensation behavior and measured density may differ in real teeth. In addition, the study was limited to a single bioceramic material (Well-Root™ PT) and three specific ultrasonic activation durations; results may not be directly generalizable to other calcium silicate-based cements or activation protocols. The influence of ultrasonic activation on hydration kinetics and internal water distribution was not directly assessed and warrants future investigation. Finally, although prolonged ultrasonic activation improved density, the clinical significance of this increase in terms of long-term sealing ability and treatment success remains to be confirmed *in vivo*.

Furthermore, the density calibration was performed using a pair of hydroxyapatite phantoms, scanned under

identical parameters as the samples. Although HA phantoms are the current standard reference for mineral-density quantification in dental micro-CT studies, it is acknowledged that the radiopacity of Well-Root™ PT differs from pure hydroxyapatite. Therefore, the reported density values represent relative mineral density calibrated against HA rather than absolute material density. This calibration approach may slightly underestimate or overestimate the true density of the bioceramic material. However, it allows consistent and reproducible comparisons across all experimental groups included in the study.

Conclusion

This *in vitro* study demonstrated that indirect ultrasonic activation influences the micro-CT density of Well-Root™ PT apical plugs in simulated immature teeth. The 15 s ultrasonic activation produced the highest median density (10.8 g/cm³), which was statistically comparable to manual condensation (11.3 g/cm³, $p = 0.98$) and significantly higher than the 3 s and 9 s activation groups (both 10.4 g/cm³, $p < 0.05$). These findings indicate that prolonged indirect ultrasonic vibration optimizes particle packing, possibly expels entrapped air and excess water, and enhances calcium silicate hydrate reorganization, resulting in superior microstructural homogeneity.

In clinical practice, the use of 15 s indirect ultrasonic activation during the placement of bioceramic apical plugs may improve apical seal quality. However, short-duration activation (3–9 s) did not offer better density than manual condensation. Additional *in vivo* studies are necessary to determine whether these density benefits translate into improved clinical performance under physiological loading and microbial challenge.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

KH - design and methodology of the study, experimental part, data analysis; RBG - methodology, data interpretation, and writing the manuscript. Both authors wrote, read, and approved the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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